

Stock Assessment Form of Red mullet (*M. barbatus*) in GSA 16

Reference year:2018

Reporting year:2019

Red mullet, *Mullus barbatus*, is an important commercial species for demersal fisheries in the Strait of Sicily (GFCM-GSAs12-16, south-central Mediterranean Sea). It is fished almost exclusively by trawling on continental-shelf bottoms. Based on available knowledge red mullets inhabiting the continental shelf of GSA 16 are considered as a stock unit with average annual landings for the period 2006-2019 of about 550 tons. Catch at age data for the period 2006-2018 has been used to assess the *Mullus barbatus* stock in the GSA 16. The assessment was performed by extended survivor analysis (XSA) by using FLR in R with MEDITS data for tuning. The stock resulted in Sustainable Exploitation status ($F_{curr} < F_{0.1}$) with high biomass values.

Stock Assessment Form version 1.0 (January 2014)

Uploader: *Danilo Scannella*

Stock assessment form

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1 Basic Identification Data

Scientific name:	Common name:	ISCAAP Group:
<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	[Red mullet]	MUT[33]
1st Geographical sub-area:	2nd Geographical sub-area:	3rd Geographical sub-area:
[GSA16]		
4th Geographical sub-area:	5th Geographical sub-area:	6th Geographical sub-area:
1st Country	2nd Country	3rd Country
[Italy]		
4thCountry	5thCountry	6thCountry
Stock assessment method: (direct, indirect, combined, none)		
Indirect method (XSA) tuned with trawl survey data		
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The ISSCAAP code is assigned according to the FAO 'International Standard Statistical Classification for Aquatic Animals and Plants' (ISSCAAP) which divides commercial species into 50 groups on the basis of their taxonomic, ecological and economic characteristics. This can be provided by the GFCM secretariat if needed. A list of groups can be found here:

<http://www.fao.org/fishery/collection/asfis/en>

2 Stock identification and biological information

2.1 Stock unit

Red mullet is distributed in the eastern Atlantic, along the European and African coasts from the North Sea and England to Senegal and in the Mediterranean and Black Sea (Fischer et al., 1987). It is a benthic species, frequently found on muddy bottoms at depths between 5 and 250 m (Voliani, 1999). Red mullet is also found on gravel, maerl and sandy bottoms. On the northern side of the Strait of Sicily (GSAs 15 and 16), this species was found almost exclusively over the shelf (44 to 69 % of the hauls) (SAMED, 2002).

Levi et al. (1992), comparing the growth curves of *M. barbatus* in the Mediterranean, found significant differences between populations on the Sicilian side of the Strait of Sicily (GSAs 15 and 16) and those in the Gulf of Gabès (GSA 14). Other evidence supporting the existence of separate stocks of red mullets in the central Mediterranean comes from parasitological observations. A large infestation by a trematode of the genus *Stephanostomum* seriously affected the red mullet fishery in Tunisian waters for several months in 1990. No such occurrence was noted in the fish landed at the Sicilian base-ports of the Strait of Sicily (Levi et al., 1993). Levi et al. (1995) reinforced the hypothesis on the existence of two separate stock units in the Strait of Sicily on the basis of the independence of the water masses and the circulation on the Sicilian and African sides of the Strait of Sicily. Since the red mullet is a typical coastal resource, the peculiarity of the Strait of Sicily (two shelves – the European and the African – separated by narrow deep bottoms) supports the hypothesis of the existence of different subpopulations in the area.

More recently connectivity between spawning and nursery areas of red mullets in the Strait of Sicily were simulated using a physical oceanographic model (Gargano et al., 2017) (Figure 2.1). Red mullet larvae were represented as Lagrangian drifters released in known spawning areas and reaching the known nurseries for settlement after a larval dispersal of 30–45 days. The numerical simulations revealed a weak degree of connectivity between the Sicilian–Maltese and the African sides of the SoS. Furthermore, red mullets around Maltese Island resulted little connected with those living off the Sicilian coast.

Based on the above considerations and in agreement with the last benchmark assessment carried out in 2018, red mullets inhabiting the GSA 16 were considered as a single stock (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the simulated larval drift of red mullet in the Sicilian and African shelves of the SoS. Close spawning areas showing similar dispersal patterns are aggregated in larger reproductive spatial units. Arrows schematize drift from spawning to nursery areas, and curved arrows illustrate possible retention regions (self-recruitment processes). The spatial distribution of the red mullet stock unit in GSA 16 is showed in green. (From Gargano et al., 2017).

Figure 2.2: The Geographical sub-areas 16 (GSA16) is highlighted in yellow.

2.2 Growth and maturity

According to Voliani (1999), the maximum total length (TL) of red mullet in the Mediterranean is 28–29 cm for females and 23 cm for males, however specimens from 10 to 20 cm TL are generally found in the commercial fisheries landings. In the northern sector (GSAs 15 and 16) the observed maximum length is 25 cm TL for females and 25 cm TL for males. Red mullet reproduction in GSA 13 occurs near the coast, from May to June–July (Gharbia and Ktari, 1981; Cherif et al., 2007b). According to

Levi (1991), spawning of red mullets in GSAs 15 and 16 take place in May.

Eggs, larvae and post-larvae up to 30–35 mm, of *M. barbatus*, are pelagic and live in the surface waters (Montalenti, 1933). According to Sabatés and Palomera (1987), larvae are found only in surface waters (0–1.5 m depth), mainly in areas influenced by river outflow. Larvae were found in the Mediterranean mainly between June and July (Lago de Lanzos, 1980; Sabatés and Palomera, 1987).

Juveniles up to 4–5 cm TL are pelagic, have a blue livery and may be collected several miles off the coast. Above this size, juveniles move to the coastal areas and become demersal. Their livery gradually changes from the juvenile to the adult colors when settling (Voliani, 1999).

Table - 2.1: Maximum size, size at first maturity and size at recruitment.

Somatic magnitude measured (LT, LC, etc)				Units	
Sex	Fem	Mal	Combined	Reproduction season	Spring-summer
Maximum size observed	25	25	25	Recruitment season	Autumn
Size at first maturity	14.16	13.85	12.38	Spawning area	Continental shelf
Recruitment size to the fishery			7	Nursery area	Coastal areas

Table - 2.2: M vector and proportion of matures by size or age (Combined sex)

Size/Age	Natural mortality	Proportion of matures
0	1.73	0.00
1	0.90	1.00
2	0.67	1.00
3	0.57	1.00
4	0.50	1.00
5	0.47	1.00

Table - 2.3: Growth and length weight model parameters

		Units	Sex			Years
			female	male	Combined	
Growth model	L_{∞}	cm			24.1	
	K				0.42	
	t_0	year			-0.8	
	Data source	Fiorentino F., (Unpubl)				
Length weight relationship	a				0.001	
	b				3.0421	

3 Fisheries information

3.1 Description of the fleet

Red mullet (*M. barbatus*) is one of the main coastal demersal resources in the Mediterranean. It is fished by otter trawls, trammel nets and gillnets (Voliani, 1999; Griffiths et al., 2007). Red mullets are caught together with other important species, such as *Mullus surmuletus* (striped red mullet), *Merluccius merluccius* (European hake), *Pagellus spp.* (seabreams, pandoras), *Uranoscopus scaber* (stargazer), *Raja spp.* (rays), *Trachinus spp.* (weevers), *Octopus vulgaris* (common octopus), *Sepia officinalis* (common cuttlefish), *Eledone spp.* (horned and musky octopuses), and *Lophius spp.* (anglerfish). In the GSA 16 (Southern coast of Sicily) red mullets are fished almost exclusively by two fleet segments of trawlers operating on continental shelf bottoms (Table 3.1). The total average annual landings in the period 2006-2018 was about 550 tons.

Table - 3.1: Description of operational units exploiting the stock in GSA 16.

	Country	GSA	Fleet Segment	Fishing Gear Class	Group of Target Species	Species
Operational Unit 1	ITA	16	T11 - Trawls	OTB	Demersal slope species	MUT
Operational Unit 2	ITA	16	T12 - Trawls	OTB	Demersal slope species	MUT

Table - 3.2: Catch, and effort by operational unit in the 2018 in GSA 16.

Operational Units*	Fleet (n° of boats)*	Catch (T of the species assessed)	Other species caught (names and weight)	Discards (species assessed)	Discards (other species caught)	Effort (GT*DaysAtSea)
Operational Unit 1		423		5.9		1535116
Operational Unit 2		86		NA		2355527
Total		509				3890642

3.2 Historical trends

Time series of landings of trawlers per length segments in the GSA16 are reported in figure 3.1.

The fishing effort of Sicilian trawlers operating in the GSA 16 in terms of GT (gross tonnage) per number of days at sea is shown in figure 3.2. It is very clear that during the time series considered fishing effort in the area decreases, which is mainly due to the reduction of distant trawler effort.

Figure 1.1: Catch in tons of red mullet (MUT) from 2006 to 2018 in the Strait of Sicily, Central Mediterranean (GSA 16).

Figure 3.2: Fishing effort, in terms of GT*DayAtSea of Sicilian trawlers based in GSA 16 from 2006 to 2018.

3.3 Management regulations

The Mediterranean Regulation EC 1967 of 21 December 2006 fixed a minimum harvest size of 11 cm TL for Red mullet and a minimum mesh size of 40 mm square or 50 mm diamond for EU bottom trawling vessels.

Furthermore, a multiannual management plan for 2008-2013 has been agreed for Italian trawlers

fishing in the Strait of Sicily. Italian Management Fishery Plans (IMAP) was mainly based on:

- a fleet reduction of 25% of the current capacity obtained in two steps. The first (12.5%) from 2008 to 2010, and the second (12.5%) from 2011 to 2013.
- a trawling ban of 45 days per year between September and October.

The IMAP was updated in January 2018. The new IMAP based regulation mainly on the reduction of fishing effort of 5 % and 10 % of fishing days in 2018.

Although the IMAP foresees an interruption of fishing for 45 consecutive days, the effective duration of the ban was 30 days per year.

In 2009, a compulsory trawling ban of 30 consecutive days was decreed for all trawlers registered in Sicily, between August and September (for trawlers registered in Mazara del Vallo), between September and October (for trawlers registered elsewhere in Sicily) and in September (for pelagic trawlers).

In 2010 the mandatory trawling ban of 30 consecutive days could be implemented from August 1st to October 17th.

In 2011 the high sea trawlers have stopped for 30 consecutive days starting from 30th August, while all the other trawlers for 30 consecutive days from 30th September.

In 2012, the compulsory temporary interruption of trawling was fixed in 30 consecutive days, beginning in the timeframe between 3rd August and 2nd October.

The trawling ban of 2013 has foreseen 30 consecutive days to start from 20 September and until 30 October for the high sea trawlers while 30 consecutive days have been scheduled to start between 6 and 24 August for coastal trawlers. According to the local PDG, the 30 days ban was adopted from the 1st to the 30th of September for the trawlers registered in Lampedusa Island.

The temporary and compulsory interruption of trawling in 2014 was 30 consecutive days, beginning in the period from 20 September to 1 October. As for the previous year, trawling around Lampedusa Island stopped from the 1st to the 30th of September. It is worth noting that inside the area covered by the local management plan of the Pelagie Islands, it was prohibited to fish for trawlers coming from other Italian compartments.

For high sea trawlers, there was a mandatory trawling ban for 30 days, beginning between 6th and 24th August. Alternatively, the temporary interruption could commence on 15 September and be completed by 14th October.

In 2015, the compulsory trawling ban was carried out for 30 consecutive days beginning in the period from 10th to 21st September. The high sea trawlers targeted to deep water shrimps could stop fishing also in other periods but, between September and 30th October, they could not fish within 12 miles of the coast.

The trawling ban in 2016 was carried out with rules similar to those of 2015. 30 consecutive days of fishing interruption were made from 15th September to 14th October, with the exception of high sea trawlers which were able to stop for 30 consecutive days from 10 August. As for the 2015, trawling

is prohibited on any vessel between 15 September and 14 October within 12 miles of the coast.

Also for 2017 trawling has been banned in Sicilian waters within 12 miles for 30 days consecutive from 25 September to 31 October. As for the previous years, the high sea trawlers could carry out the 30 days of trawling ban by the end of 2017, starting from 7 August 2017. As for 2015 and 2016, any trawling was prohibited within 12 miles of the coast.

In 2018, the mandatory trawling ban for 30 consecutive days beginning in the period from 1st August to 30st September was applied. The high sea trawlers targeted to deep water shrimps could stop fishing for 30 days from 1st August to the end of the year but, between 1st August to 31st October, they could not fish within 12 miles of the coast.

3.4 Reference points

4 Fisheries independent information

4.1 Trawl survey

In order to collect fisheries independent data, which is a requirement of the EU DCF (Council Regulation 199/2008, Commission Regulation 655/2008, Commission Decision EC 949/2008 and Commission Decision 93/2010) the MEDITS international trawl survey is carried out in GSAs 16 on an annual basis since 1994.

4.1.1 Brief description of the direct method used

Distribution, abundance and demographic information of the stock at sea were derived from data collected during the MEDITS surveys carried out annually in the GSA 16 from 1994 to 2018 in spring/early summer. It worth to note that in 2013, 2014 and 2017 the Medits survey was carried out in the autumn season between September and December for administrative constrains. Since 2004, a total of 120 hauls have been performed yearly (Figure 4.1). The area covered is about 31400 km² within the 10-800 m depth-range. The sampling design is random stratified with an allocation of hauls proportional to strata extension (depth strata: 10-50 m, 51-100 m, 101-200 m, 201-500 m, 501-800 m). Roughly the same haul positions were kept each year. The standardized GOC 73 trawl net is used with mesh size in the cod-end 20 mm opening and the vertical opening of the mouth of 2.4-2.9 m. More details on the MEDITS protocol is reported in the MEDITS-Handbook. Version n. 9 (2017).

Direct methods: trawl based abundance indices (GSA16)

Table - 4.1: Trawl survey basic information

Survey	MEDITS	Trawler/RV	TRAWLER
Sampling season	MAY-JULY		
Sampling design	Stratified with number of haul by stratum proportional to stratum surface (see MEDITS-Handbook. Revision n. 9, 2017, MEDITS Working Group: 106 pp.)		
Sampler (gear used)	Bottom trawl made of four panels (IFREMER reference GOC 73)		
Cod –end mesh size as opening in mm	10 mm mesh size, which corresponds to ~ 20 mm of mesh opening		
Investigated depth range (m)	10-800m		

Table - 4.2: Trawl survey sampling area and number of hauls

Stratum	Total surface (km ²)	Trawlable surface (km ²)	Swept area (km ²)	Number of hauls
a	2979	na	na	11
b	5943	na	na	23
c	5565	na	na	21
d	6972	na	na	27
e	9927	na	na	38
Total	31384	na	na	120

Figure 4.3: Map of hauls positions in the Strait of Sicily (GSA16).

Table - 4.3: Trawl survey biomass and abundance and results in GSA 16. Since the species inhabits exclusively the shelf bottoms, only the density for the 10-200 m depth stratum is reported.

Depth Stratum	Years	kg per km ²	CV or other	N per km ²	CV or other
10-200 m	1994	3	61	60	52.6
10-200 m	1995	5.2	49.2	123	48.4
10-200 m	1996	12.4	48.8	348	49.3
10-200 m	1997	7.2	37.1	199	36.6
10-200 m	1998	5.5	44.3	143	43.3
10-200 m	1999	10	58.4	240	61.4
10-200 m	2000	9.6	54.5	382	55.2
10-200 m	2001	26.6	74.6	579	72.6
10-200 m	2002	14.5	48.3	586	42.3
10-200 m	2003	23.7	43.5	5155	54.9
10-200 m	2004	22.7	28.1	659	28.2
10-200 m	2005	24.8	55.9	1592	62.1
10-200 m	2006	22	59.1	564	56.4
10-200 m	2007	29.1	39.9	802	37.6
10-200 m	2008	34.4	49.8	778	46.9
10-200 m	2009	35.9	36.8	978	35.2
10-200 m	2010	36	62	900	52.6
10-200 m	2011	25.5	39.6	1121	60.5
10-200 m	2012	21.9	37.8	650	40.3
10-200 m	2013	43.6	55.9	4062	96.6
10-200 m	2014	39.9	37.4	2181	41.1
10-200 m	2015	8.3	30.3	209	33
10-200 m	2016	20.8	47.4	734	48
10-200 m	2017	38.5	42.1	1635	35
10-200 m	2018	41.1	37.0	5245	55

Direct methods: trawl based length/age structure of population at sea

Slicing method

Length structures (Figure 4.2, 4.3) were converted into Age structure by using Age Length Key based on otolith reading. Numbers at age were raised to the overall shelf area of GSA 16, assuming the same catchability.

Figure 4.2 – Length frequency distributions (LFD) of MUT from 2006 to 2018 per segments <24m in GSA 16, combined sex.

FLD OTB>24m

Source: IRBIM-CNR SS Mazara del Vallo

Figure 4.3 – Length frequency distributions (LFD) of MUT from 2006 to 2018 per segments >24m in GSA 16, combined sex.

Table - 4.4: Age structure of population at sea (thousand).

AGE	N (sex combined) by Age class (thousands)												
	Year												
	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
0	1174.4	1515.8	555.6	172.3	576.9	42.7	79.0	63.7	398.7	282.2	163.5	1520.6	3046.1
1	5688.0	7388.2	6862.3	2460.8	965.0	2025.6	2547.9	1474.8	1957.2	412.5	1331.3	2378.7	2103.1
2	7665.0	9866.3	9773.7	9091.2	5977.5	5729.1	4933.4	2757.7	3138.0	2125.6	2926.3	4611.1	3088.3
3	2607.8	2367.1	3228.0	2549.5	2884.8	1468.3	2251.0	1435.0	2226.6	1406.4	2126.8	2732.5	2076.5
4	517.9	378.3	464.6	227.4	747.4	329.8	553.7	417.9	421.6	547.1	648.3	1085.8	683.3
5	44.9	36.2	16.0	24.8	135.4	39.1	65.0	46.0	56.4	67.0	565.4	2409.4	662.2
Tot	1174.4	1515.8	555.6	172.3	576.9	42.7	79.0	63.7	398.7	282.2	163.5	1520.6	3046.1

Table - 4.5: Sex ratio per years of Red mullet from MEDITS in GSA 16. All year combined.

Sex ratio	Year												
	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
Total	0.5	0.52	0.56	0.49	0.54	0.53	0.54	0.52	0.57	0.55	0.52	0.52	0.48
	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	
	0.51	0.5	0.47	0.45	0.55	0.51	0.49	0.59	0.48	0.45	0.55	0.58	

Direct methods: trawl based Recruitment analysis

Table - 4.6: Trawl surveys; recruitment analysis summary

Survey	MEDITS	Trawler/RV	S.Anna/Pegaso
Survey season			Spring/summer
Cod –end mesh size as opening in mm			20 mm
Investigated depth range (m)			10-800m
Recruitment season and peak (months)			Autumn
Age at fishing-grounds recruitment			Age 0
Length at fishing-grounds recruitment			7 cm

4.1.2 Spatial distribution of the resources

According to Garofalo et al. (2004), two major and clearly separate spawning areas exist on the northern side of the Strait of Sicily (GSAs 15 and 16). They are located over the Adventure Bank, off the southwestern coast of Sicily (GSA 16) and over the Malta Bank, between Sicily and the Maltese Islands (GSA 15), respectively, on the outer shelf (100–150 m depth) (Figure 4.4). Recent research on the Marine Protected Area of Castellammare del Golfo (northwestern coast of Sicily – GSA10), where trawling has been forbidden since 1990, has shown that the oldest spawners prefer deeper bottoms (100–200 m depth), whereas the young ones are found in shallower areas (<50m depth) (Fiorentino et al., 2008). Although recruits exhibited a widespread distribution throughout the coastal waters, four main areas showing high abundance and the almost exclusive presence of recruits were found within GSA 16 (southwestern coast of Sicily), between 20 and 50 m depth (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.4: Map of the average distribution of *M. barbatus* spawners. The contour (solid black line) of the overall study area and the water depth of more than 800 m (hatched areas) are also shown (GSAs 15 and 16) (from Garofalo et al., 2004).

Figure 4.5: Map of the average distribution of *M. barbatus* spawners. The contour (solid black line) of the overall study area and the water depth of more than 800 m (hatched areas) are also shown (GSAs 15 and 16) (from Garofalo et al., 2004).

4.1.3 Historical trends

The time series of biomass index (BI) from MEDITS trawl surveys is showing a general increasing trend since 1994. Strong fluctuation was observed in the last years, with 2015 lower than the 33th percentile (14.3 kg/km²), 2017 and 2018 higher than the 66th percentile (25.7 kg/km²) and 2016 at an intermediate level (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: The chart shows the historical trend of biomass index expressed as kilograms on square kilometer derived from MEDITS data from 1994 to 2018. With the purple and green line, the thirty-third and sixty-sixth percentiles are represented respectively

5 Ecological information

5.1 Protected species potentially affected by the fisheries

A list of protected species that can be potentially affected by the fishery should be incorporated here. This should also be completed with the potential effect and if available an associated value (e.g. bycatch of these species in T)

5.2 Environmental indexes

If any environmental index is used as i) a proxy for recruitment strength, ii) a proxy for carrying capacity, or any other index that is incorporated in the assessment, then it should be included here.

Other environmental indexes that are considered important for the fishery (e.g. Chla or other that may affect catchability, etc.) can be reported here.

6 Stock Assessment

An extended survivor analysis (XSA) as implemented in the FLR (fisheries libraries in R) was performed.

Catch data (landings and discards) from 2006 to 2017 of Sicilian trawlers were collected within DCF. Considering that about half of distant trawlers fleet fished outside the GSA16 the catch data (landings) for this fleet was reduced by 50%. For calibration (Tuning data) MEDITS trawl survey data were used from GSA 16 at the same time series. Natural mortality was estimated by Gislason's method (Gislason et al., 2013). The annual size of the landings as well as Medits data were converted into the number at age by Length Age Key obtained from commercial catch.

6.1 Extended survivor analysis (XSA)

6.1.1 Model assumptions

Darby and Flatman (1994) outline the XSA algorithm as performing the following steps: (1) a cohort analysis of the total catch-at-age data to produce estimates of population abundance-at-age, and total fishing mortalities; (2) adjustment of the CPUE values for the period of fishing defined using the alpha and beta parameters in the fleet tuning file, into CPUE values that would have been recorded if the fleet had fished only at the beginning of the year. The adjusted values are directly comparable with the population abundances at the beginning of the year; (3) calculation of fleet-based estimates of population abundance-at-age from the adjusted CPUE values and fleet catchabilities; (4) calculation of a least-squares estimate (weighted mean) of the terminal population (survivors at the end of the final assessment year) for each cohort in the tuning range using the fleet-derived estimates of population abundance-at-age. These terminal populations are used to initiate the Cohort analysis in the next iteration. The process iterates until the convergence criteria described for ad-hoc tuning are achieved. Various options are available for catchability analysis, time series weighting and shrinkage of the weighted estimates.

6.1.2 Scripts

The best model adopted in the last benchmark to run XSA was used in order to update Red mullet assessment in the time series from 2006 to 2018. The script is here reported:

```
FLXSA.control.MUT<-FLXSA.control(x=NULL,tol=1e-09, maxit=30, min.nse=0.3, fse=2, rage=1, qage=3, shk.n=TRUE, shk.f=TRUE, shk.yrs=2, shk.ages=2, window=100, tsrange=20, tspower=0, vpa=TRUE)
```

6.1.3 Input data and Parameters

The growth parameters used for VBGF were the ones reported in table 2.3. Total catches (Table 6.1) and catch numbers at age from GSA16 were used as input data (Table 6.2). SOP correction was applied to catch numbers at age. Discard was not included in the analysis as it was negligible.

Table - 6.1: Red mullet in GSA 16. Landings in tons

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
GSA16	774	883	791	580	546	468	500	323	353	436	411	576	509

Table - 6.2: Red mullet in GSA 16. Catch by ages matrix in thousand.

YEAR	AGE					
	0	1	2	3	4	5
2006	1174.4	5688.0	7665.0	2607.8	517.9	44.9
2007	1515.8	7388.2	9866.3	2367.1	378.3	36.2
2008	555.6	6862.3	9773.7	3228.0	464.6	16.0
2009	172.3	2460.8	9091.2	2549.5	227.4	24.8
2010	576.9	965.0	5977.5	2884.8	747.4	135.4
2011	42.7	2025.6	5729.1	1468.3	329.8	39.1
2012	79.0	2547.9	4933.4	2251.0	553.7	65.0
2013	63.7	1474.8	2757.7	1435.0	417.9	46.0
2014	398.7	1957.2	3138.0	2226.6	421.6	56.4
2015	282.2	412.5	2125.6	1406.4	547.1	67.0
2016	163.5	1331.3	2926.3	2126.8	648.3	565.4
2017	1520.6	2378.7	4611.1	2732.5	1085.8	2409.4
2018	3046.1	2103.1	3088.3	2076.5	683.3	662.2

Table - 6.3: Red mullet in GSA 16. Tuning series at age as n/kmq

age	0	1	2	3	4	5
2006	52.0	109.7	96.0	19.0	2.1	0.3
2007	74.4	124.5	155.3	36.6	11.1	0.7
2008	27.1	191.7	210.1	65.8	8.7	1.1
2009	50.2	181.3	202.2	42.5	6.1	0.7
2010	73.8	128.9	186.7	46.1	8.4	1.4
2011	101.2	115.6	75.1	19.8	4.9	0.6
2012	112.8	154.0	59.9	14.3	2.6	0.3
2013	646.3	161.8	78.9	23.5	6.7	1.8
2014	583.2	153.9	87.3	37.6	5.2	0.4
2015	29.4	24.1	34.4	11.3	3.4	0.5
2016	27.4	148.0	58.8	13.1	2.6	0.2
2017	465.4	91.5	97.8	39.0	9.9	0.8
2018	2251.8	193.4	89.4	43.3	11.7	20.0

Table - 6.4: Red mullet in GSA 16. Mean weight (kg) at age

age	0	1	2	3	4	5
2006	0.01	0.029	0.053	0.08	0.107	0.141
2007	0.007	0.03	0.053	0.084	0.108	0.129
2008	0.006	0.03	0.052	0.081	0.103	0.126
2009	0.009	0.031	0.053	0.081	0.104	0.127
2010	0.01	0.033	0.054	0.082	0.105	0.128
2011	0.01	0.035	0.052	0.081	0.104	0.125
2012	0.01	0.033	0.052	0.082	0.105	0.128
2013	0.007	0.034	0.053	0.083	0.106	0.127
2014	0.009	0.03	0.055	0.082	0.106	0.134
2015	0.009	0.03	0.055	0.082	0.106	0.134

2016	0.009	0.03	0.055	0.082	0.106	0.134
2017	0.009	0.03	0.055	0.082	0.106	0.134
2018	0.009	0.03	0.055	0.082	0.106	0.134

Table - 6.5: Red mullet in GSA 16. Natural Mortality at age estimated by Gislason's method.

Group 0	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
1.73	0.90	0.67	0.57	0.50	0.47

Table - 6.6: Red mullet in GSA 16. Proportion of mature specimens at age.

Age0	Age 1	Age 2	Age 3	Age 4	Age 5
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

6.1.4 Results

$F_{\text{bar}(1-3)}$ values estimated by final model are reported in the table 6.7.

Table - 6.7: XSA estimates of fishing mortality at age.

Age	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
0	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02
1	0.15	0.19	0.17	0.09	0.03	0.09	0.11	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.05	0.07	0.06
2	0.71	0.85	0.73	0.73	0.74	0.62	0.67	0.34	0.36	0.38	0.29	0.30	0.36
3	0.87	0.86	1.21	0.69	1.15	0.83	0.92	0.78	0.73	1.04	0.65	0.55	0.57
4	1.73	0.42	0.52	0.33	0.78	0.66	1.48	0.70	0.72	1.69	1.62	0.88	0.64
5	1.73	0.42	0.52	0.33	0.78	0.66	1.48	0.70	0.72	1.69	1.62	0.88	0.64
$F_{\text{bar}(1-3)}$	0.57	0.63	0.70	0.51	0.64	0.51	0.57	0.40	0.39	0.48	0.33	0.31	0.33

Spawning stock biomass (SSB), Total biomass and Recruitment estimates by XSA models are shown in table 6.8. In the last years the SSB increased (Figure 6.1) whilst recruitment decreased (Figure 6.2), being both values in the highest percentile of the time series.

Table - 6.8: Main results of the XSA final model.

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Fbar	0.86	0.58	0.66	0.46	0.67	0.55	0.80	0.48	0.47	0.78	0.65	0.45	0.41
TB (t)	6190	4878	3397	3702	3586	3596	3348	2991	3426	3699	3928	4232	4173
SSB (t)	2959	2907	2307	1827	1859	1851	1770	1673	1832	1888	2354	2284	2613
Rec (thous.)	323.1	281.5	181.7	208.3	172.7	174.4	157.8	188.3	177.2	201.2	174.9	278.4	222.7

Table - 6.9: Critical percentiles of the XSA final model.

	Fbar	TB (tons)	SSB(Tons)	Rec
33th per.	0.48	3580	1851	177081
66th per.	0.66	3909	2305	207749

Figure 6.1: The chart shows the SSB estimated values by XSA model. With the red dotted line the sixty-sixth percentiles is represented.

Figure 6.2: The chart shows the Recruitment estimated values by XSA model. With the red dotted line the sixty-sixth percentiles is represented.

Yield per Recruit

A yield per recruit analysis was carried using the FLBRP library (FLR) to calculate $F_{0.1}$. The estimated $F_{0.1}$ value was 0.44 (Figure 6.3). Instead, the estimated $F_{0.1}$ value in last benchmark assessment was 0.42. These value resulted within the range reported for the species in the Mediterranean.

Figure 6.3: The charts show the outcomes of yield per recruit analysis

6.1.5 Robustness analysis

Log Residuals at age for survey analysis obtained with XSA models are reported in figure 6.4. The residuals do not show any particular trend

Figure 6.4: Log residuals at age for survey analysis obtained with XSA models.

6.1.6 Retrospective analysis

Retrospective analyses showed rather consistent results, although a clear sensitivity of stock dynamics assessment to the last years is evident (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5: Retrospective analysis of Red mullet stock in GSA 16

6.1.7 Assessment quality

Stability of the assessment, evaluation of quality of the data and reliability of model assumptions were considered good by the Working Group.

6.2 Short term predictions

A deterministic short term forecast for the period 2018 to 2021 was performed using the FLR routines provided by JRC and based on the results of the assessment performed during the GFCM WG. The input parameters were the same used for the XSA stock assessment. An average of the last three years has been used for weight at age, maturity at age and F at age (Table 24).

Table - 6.10: Short term forecast by different F scenarios of Red mullet stock and catch in GSA 16.

	Ffactor	Fbar	Catch 2018	Catch 2019	Catch 2020	Catch 2021	SSB_2020	SSB_2021	Change_SSB 2020-2021(%)
1	0	0.00	509	381	0	0	2635	3014	14
2	0.1	0.03	509	381	49	67	2635	2973	13
3	0.2	0.06	509	381	95	127	2635	2934	11
4	0.3	0.10	509	381	141	182	2635	2897	10
5	0.4	0.13	509	381	184	231	2635	2861	9
6	0.5	0.16	509	381	226	276	2635	2826	7
7	0.6	0.19	509	381	267	316	2635	2793	6
8	0.7	0.23	509	381	307	353	2635	2761	5
9	0.8	0.26	509	381	345	386	2635	2730	4
10	0.9	0.29	509	381	382	416	2635	2700	2
11	1	0.32	509	381	417	443	2635	2672	1
12	1.1	0.35	509	381	452	468	2635	2644	0
13	1.2	0.39	509	381	485	491	2635	2617	-1
14	1.3	0.42	509	381	518	512	2635	2591	-2
15	1.4	0.45	509	381	549	531	2635	2567	-3
16	1.5	0.48	509	381	580	548	2635	2543	-4
17	1.6	0.52	509	381	609	563	2635	2519	-4
18	1.7	0.55	509	381	638	578	2635	2497	-5
19	1.8	0.58	509	381	666	591	2635	2475	-6
20	1.9	0.61	509	381	693	603	2635	2454	-7
21	2	0.64	509	381	720	614	2635	2434	-8
22	F0.1	0.44	509	381	543	527	2635	2571	-2

6.3 Medium term predictions

6.4 Long term predictions

7 Draft scientific advice

Based on	Indicator	Analytic al reference point(name and value)	Current value from the analysis(name and value)	Empirical reference value(name and value)	Trend(time period)	Stock Status
Fishing mortality	Fishing mortality	$F_{0.1} = 0.44$ $F_{0.1} = 0.42$ (2018-benchmark)	$F_{curr} = 0.32$		D (from 2015 to 2018)	S
	Fishing effort				D (from 2007 to 2018)	
	Catch				D (from 2017 to 2018)	
Stock abundance	Biomass (Kg/Km ²) from Trawl Survey		38.5 ($B_{current}$)	13.4 (33 th perc.le) 25.7 (66 th perc.le)	I (from 1994)	O_H
	Total biomass (tons) from XSA		4173($B_{current}$)	3580 (33 th perc.le) 3909 (66 th perc.le)	D (from 2006 to 2013); I (from 2014 to 2018)	O_H
	SSB (tons) from XSA		2613 ($SBB_{current}$)	1851 (33 th perc.le) 2305 (66 th perc.le)	D (from 2006 to 2013); I (from 2014 to 2018)	O_H
Recruitment	Rec (thousand) from XSA		222748($ReC_{current}$)	177081 (33 th perc.le) 207749 (66 th perc.le)	D (from 2006 to 2012); I (from 2013 to 2018)	

Final Diagnosis	The ratio $F_{curr}/F_{0.1}$ ($F_{0.1}$ referred to last benchmark) is equal to 0.72, the stock status is in Sustainable Exploitation with Relative High Biomass.					

State the rationale behind that diagnoses, explaining if it is based on analytical or on empirical references

7.1 Explanation of codes

Trend categories

- 1) N - No trend
- 2) I - Increasing
- 3) D – Decreasing
- 4) C - Cyclic

Stock Status

Based on Fishing mortality related indicators

- 1) **N - Not known or uncertain** – Not much information is available to make a judgment;
- 2) **U - undeveloped or new fishery** - Believed to have a significant potential for expansion in total production;
- 3) **S - Sustainable exploitation**- fishing mortality or effort below an agreed fishing mortality or effort based Reference Point;
- 4) **IO –In Overfishing status**– fishing mortality or effort above the value of the agreed fishing mortality or effort based Reference Point. An agreed range of overfishing levels is provided;

Range of Overfishing levels based on fishery reference points

In order to assess the level of overfishing status when $F_{0.1}$ from a Y/R model is used as LRP, the following operational approach is proposed:

- If $F_c^*/F_{0.1}$ is below or equal to 1.33 the stock is in (**O_L**): **Low overfishing**
- If the $F_c/F_{0.1}$ is between 1.33 and 1.66 the stock is in (**O_I**): **Intermediate overfishing**
- If the $F_c/F_{0.1}$ is equal or above to 1.66 the stock is in (**O_H**): **High overfishing**

* F_c is current level of F

- 5) **C- Collapsed**- no or very few catches;

Based on Stock related indicators

- 1) **N - Not known or uncertain**: Not much information is available to make a judgment
- 2) **S - Sustainably exploited**: Standing stock above an agreed biomass based Reference Point;
- 3) **O - Overexploited**: Standing stock below the value of the agreed biomass based Reference Point. An agreed range of overexploited status is provided;

Empirical Reference framework for the relative level of stock biomass index

- **Relative low biomass**: Values lower than or equal to 33rd percentile of biomass index in the time series (**O_L**)
- **Relative intermediate biomass**: Values falling within this limit and 66th percentile (**O_I**)
- **Relative high biomass**: Values higher than the 66th percentile (**O_H**)

- 4) **D–Depleted:** Standing stock is at lowest historical levels, irrespective of the amount of fishing effort exerted;
- 5) **R –Recovering:** Biomass are increasing after having been depleted from a previous period;

Agreed definitions as per SAC Glossary

Overfished (or overexploited) - A stock is considered to be overfished when its abundance is below an agreed biomass based reference target point, like $B_{0.1}$ or $BMSY$. To apply this denomination, it should be assumed that the current state of the stock (in biomass) arises from the application of excessive fishing pressure in previous years. This classification is independent of the current level of fishing mortality.

Stock subjected to overfishing (or overexploitation) - A stock is subjected to overfishing if the fishing mortality applied to it exceeds the one it can sustainably stand, for a longer period. In other words, the current fishing mortality exceeds the fishing mortality that, if applied during a long period, under stable conditions, would lead the stock abundance to the reference point of the target abundance (either in terms of biomass or numbers)